

Developing Distributed Collaborative Applications with HTML5 under the Coupled Objects Paradigm

Nelson Baloian

(Department of Computer Science, University of Chile, Santiago de Chile, Chile
nbaloian@dcc.uchile.cl)

Diego Aguirre

(Department of Computer Science, University of Chile, Santiago de Chile, Chile
diaguirr@dcc.uchile.cl)

Gustavo Zurita

(Department of Management Control and Information Systems, Faculty of Economics and
Business, University of Chile, Santiago de Chile, Chile
gzurita@fen.uchile.cl)

Abstract: One of the main tasks in developing distributed collaborative systems is to support synchronization processes. The Coupled Objects paradigm has emerged as a way to easily support these processes by dynamically coupling arbitrary user interface objects between heterogeneous applications. In this article we present an architecture for developing distributed collaborative applications using HTML5 and show its usage through the design and implementation of a series of collaborative systems in different scenarios. The experience of developing and using this architecture has shown that it is easy to use, robust and has good performance.

Keywords: Coupled objects paradigm; synchronization; HTML5; mobile collaboration; distributed collaborative systems

Categories: H.3.1, H.3.2, H.3.3, H.3.7, H.5.1

1 Introduction

Collaborative systems are conceived to assist groups in communicating, in collaborating, and in coordinating their activities, either in the same physical place or distributed over many locations [Ellis, Gibbs, & Rein, 1991]. In order to support collaboration in a distributed scenario, software engineers develop distributed systems, which consist of several autonomous entities with their own local memory [Andrews, 1999], communicating with each other by message passing [Ghosh, 2006]. For enabling communication and data management in distributed applications, developers typically use middleware by encapsulating the code, implementing the low level TCP/IP communication layer between applications running on different hosts.

Since the early days of the distributed application development, the need for a middleware that could simplify the programming of distributed applications was evident since a good portion of the code necessary to implement the communication between applications could be encapsulated, thus allowing the developer to concentrate on the application's logic. One of the first of such frameworks was Sun

Microsystem's RPC [Sirinvasan, 1995] schema developed for simplifying the development of the Networked file system (NFS) for the Solaris architecture. Another of the early runners was the CORBA [Vogel & Duddy, 1995] architecture, which was developed with the aim of serving as a communication platform among applications developed for different architectures in different programming languages. However, the architecture was not well specified and various vendors implemented different versions of this architecture, which were incompatible. Among them, CORBA did not fulfill the expectations.

The aim of these systems is to make distributed applications programming not too different from the programming of stand-alone applications, by encapsulating the communication protocol and offering the programmer a nice interface for executing code on another computer.

Many other platforms and architectures have been developed thereafter [Urnes & Nejabi, 1994] for suiting a certain class of applications with common requirements. They differ on the distribution schemes of the shared data, communication mechanisms, and application architecture they support [Lukosch, 2002]. Rendezvous [Hill, et al., 1994] and Suite are groupware platforms, which use a central distribution scheme for the data of collaborative applications. GroupKit [Roseman & Greenberg, 1996], DECAF [Strom et al., 1998] and MASC [Aldunate et al., 2006] use a replicated distribution scheme. Guerrero and Fuller [Guerrero & Fuller, 2001] propose a pattern system to support the design of collaborative applications. Patterson [Patterson, 1995], Dewan [Dewan, 1995] and Roth [Roth & Unger, 2000] propose various taxonomies for groupware platforms, especially with respect to the shared data distribution schema they support. They can be grouped in the following four classes:

- **Centralized:** A single server maintains the data for all applications. Every application has to contact this server to retrieve the state of the shared work and/or make changes. This may cause bottlenecks if the server is loaded with too much synchronizing work.
- **Replicated:** Every participant has a copy of all the shared data and the application is exactly replicated at every site. The application has a better performance since it has to access local data only. However, the need to keep these data coherent and synchronized at every site may lead to very complex algorithms, especially when dealing with problems such as latecomers [Lukosch, 2003].
- **Asymmetric:** There is no pre-defined central server, but one of the participants takes that role.
- **Semi-replicated:** there are multiple servers in this schema. Compared to the Centralized schema, this may lead to a shorter response time and is more robust, since the crash of one of the servers does not imply the crash of the system. It has some of the problems of data coherence found in the replicated schema.

Thanks to the rapid development of mobile technologies, wireless networks and the sinking costs of these technologies, today, collaborative systems tend to use mobile devices for enabling and enhancing communication among the members of a

particular group. These new hardware capabilities can support ubiquitous group-work in ways that were not conceived before or were impossible to develop with desktop-based technology. However, mobile devices such as laptops, tablet PCs and smartphones usually run over different operating systems, which poses two main issues: (1) in terms of software development, it provides very few possibilities of integration; and (2) in terms of usage, they implement different human-computer interaction patterns and use different data formats (Feisst, dos Santos, Mitic, and Christ 2005). In order to overcome these problems, we claim the best strategy to follow is to implement platform-independent applications. As of today, the most promising approach seems to be HTML5, which is expected to become a major revision and future standard in the development of Web applications [Hickson, 2011].

In this article, we propose an architecture for developing distributed collaborative applications using HTML5 and we show its usage through the design and implementation of a series of collaborative systems in different scenarios. As a foundation basis, we extend the *Coupled Objects* paradigm, initially developed for desktop-based applications under the name of *MatchMaker* [Zhao & Hoppe, 1994]. The authors' experience designing and developing collaborative applications [Hoppe et al., 2000], [Sapateiro, et al., 2011], [Zurita, Baloian & Baytelman, 2006] with previous versions of this architecture [Baloian, Pino, & Jansen 2007], [Tewissen et al., 2000] show that the coupled objects approach is easy to implement and allows the development of powerful collaborative applications in an easy way

2 Related Work

The first Web applications were limited to consuming content generated by others in desktop-based services. Today, this trend has evolved to user-generated content and application platforms that are either desktop-based or mobile. The implementation of such Web applications has also evolved from plug-in technologies (such as Adobe Flash) to standard HTML5 development, new browser features, and faster JavaScript engines, among others. The extensive usage of JavaScript in today's Web applications induces the need for frameworks supporting faster development, better reusability and maintainability. As Model-View-Controller (MVC) is a well-known design pattern for server-side application development, it becomes even more important on the client side, leading to several prevalent JavaScript MVC frameworks. Therefore, JavaScript application frameworks will tend to lead the development of future Web-based business applications, including collaborative ones [Grüneberger, 2012].

Grüneberger presents a series of collaboration extension for JavaScript frameworks, as well as a prototypical implementation of these extensions in *SAPUI5* (a UI development toolkit for HTML5 development) and *KnockoutJS* (a JavaScript library that allows developers to create user interfaces with a clean underlying data model).

BackBone is a JavaScript library that eases and helps structure the process of developing HTML5-based Web applications. As other popular frameworks, it is based on the model-view-controller (MVC) application design pattern, and as a JavaScript library, it implements a RESTful JSON interface [Osmani, 2013].

This library is used for developing single-page Web applications, and for keeping synchronized various parts of Web applications, such as multiple clients and the

server. Data is represented as models, which can be created, validated, destroyed, and saved to the server. Whenever an action in the user interface causes an attribute of a model to change, the model triggers a change event; all the views that display the model's state can be notified of the change so that they are able to respond accordingly, re-rendering themselves with new information [Osmani, 2013].

3 The coupled object Paradigm

When developing distributed collaborative applications, software engineers generally deal with requirements linked to supporting synchronization either in communication, feedback or other kinds of processes. Therefore, there is a need for middleware capable of offering an easy way to develop these features rather than counting on a plain TCP/IP protocol implementation.

3.1 Synchronization Requirements in Distributed Applications

According to Tewissen et al., the typical synchronization requirements to take into account when designing and developing distributed applications for implementing collaborative learning activities in the classroom are [Tewissen et al., 2000]:

- *Dynamic synchronization*: it should be possible to start and stop the synchronization process at any point in the application's lifetime. Before and after the coupling phase, applications should continue to exist independently. This is in order to allow a swift switching from collaborative learning activities to individual learning and back.
- *Partial synchronization*: it should be possible to individually synchronize each component of an application's interface with a component of another application's interface, thus allowing the synchronization of applications with completely different interfaces. In fact, in many situations the application used by the teacher will have different functionalities from the application used by the students. In other words, this feature supports the implementation of various roles in a distributed environment.
- *Replicated architecture*: it should be possible to synchronize multiple and potentially different applications already existing in a distributed environment. This is in order to transform many already existing single user applications in collaborative applications. This also eases the implementation of collaborative applications by allowing the developer to concentrate on its functionalities instead of the synchronization.

Although these synchronization requirements were stated for a collaborative learning scenario, it is easy to see they are common to many applications. Therefore, it is good idea to develop a generic solution consisting of an architecture allowing programmers to simply develop distributed applications based on the Coupled Objects paradigm.

3.2 The Coupled Objects Paradigm

The Coupled Objects paradigm states that distributed applications can be synchronized by dynamically coupling and decoupling a set of objects of various

applications running in different hosts. When two objects are coupled, the events generated at one of these objects are automatically propagated to the rest of the coupled objects. This approach differs from more classical ones like sharing a remote single object or having a replication of one object in each application.

This paradigm supports synchronization by combining two architectures for collaborative systems: (1) a centralized server, and (2) a replicated architecture. By combining them, we get the advantages of both solutions and we remove the disadvantages. A centralized server allows for a simple and effective implementation of synchronization; a problem with a centralized server is that it is impossible for clients to continue working if it is no longer reachable. By using a replicated architecture, it is possible for an application to keep working in a standalone manner even if the server is unreachable.

3.3 Previous Implementations

In this section of the article, we briefly present the different previous implementations of the Coupled Objects paradigm:

The first version of this middleware was developed in 1993 at the GMD-IPSI institute in Darmstadt, Germany, within the research activities of the COSOFT (Computer Support for Face-to-face Teaching) research group. They intended to develop teaching/learning models and systems for supporting teaching/learning activities in an electronic classroom. In this version, coupling and communication facilities were added to an existing library established to ease the development of applications involving graphical user interfaces, including functions to couple and decouple new widgets. Communication between applications was based on a client-server model. Applications that were going to be synchronized needed to register first with the server with a distinctive name. Coupling and decoupling of objects was pairwise with objects living in different applications. The naming of objects was hierarchical, where a suffix 'one' corresponds to the first component in the hierarchy. Coupling was also hierarchical, which means that by coupling a parent object (container), all contained objects were also coupled. The library also provided a RPC facility: a callback function of a widget of any registered application could be invoked from another registered application [Zhao & Hoppe, 1994].

The second version, developed at the COLLIDE (Collaborative, Intelligent Distributed Environments) research group in Duisburg, Germany, was implemented in C/C++ over the Windows operative system and was the first one to be called *MatchMaker*. Still centered on the topic of coupled user interface objects, this new version was successfully used as one basis for software implementations in a computer-integrated classroom scenario [Hoppe et al., 2000].

The Java *MatchMaker* (JMM) implementation is a complete reimplementaion that uses Java specific features such as: RMI, Reflection, Dynamic Class Loading, and common object oriented design principles. The enhancements with respect to the previous version were mainly oriented towards integrating and taking up new standards in the field of distributed computing, thus resulting in being more compatible and more standardized [Tewissen et al., 2000].

A third implementation was developed in 2007 [Baloian, Pino & Jansen, 2007] to overcome the problem that arose when more local area networks (LAN) did not allow applications to contact other ones outside the LAN using another protocol than HTTP

for security reasons. Moreover, they also restricted applications running inside the LAN to open server sockets on ports other than those assigned to the HTTP protocol, which is port 80. This made the previous implementation very difficult to be used since it RMI uses other ports. The solution was to re-implement MatchMaker using SOAP over HyperText Transfer Protocol (HTTP) as the transportation layer for communicating clients with the server, and implementing the MatchMaker server as a Web Service. HTTP is normally open to firewalls and it is easily accessible from clients behind proxies or NATs. To accomplish this task, we used Apache Axis as the platform for Web Services and consumer clients in Java. Axis is an Open Source SOAP engine written in Java. At the sever side, Apache Axis works as a servlet, so it needs to be deployed inside a Web Servlet Container such as Jakarta Tomcat, WebLogic or the Web Application Server of J2EE. Apache Axis provides classes allowing clients to connect to a server, communicate with a remote application using the SOAP protocol and invoke Web Service methods with little effort from the developer. This new version of Match- Maker, known as SOAP MatchMaker, works the same way as the current RMI MatchMaker version. It only differs in some aspects, being the communication protocol used to exchange messages between clients and server the most notorious one.

In the RMI MatchMaker version, clients act as servers listening for events from the central server. In this new approach, the clients cannot act as servers anymore; they are forced to act in passive mode. This means clients need to contact the server to find out if new events affected the coupled objects. The basic mechanism consists of every client having an event queue at the server side. Clients are constantly requesting the server for new events, and every time a new event is available, it is sent to the client. If no new events are available, the client keeps waiting until a new event is available, but the connection with the server is kept alive.

4 Implementing the Coupled Objects Paradigm with HTML5

Over the last decade we have seen an explosion in the development of new collaborative systems using mobile devices that incorporate and utilize their communication capabilities to support collaborative work in ways that were not conceived before or were impossible to implement with desktop computers. Applications allowing users to collaborate in real time over wireless connected mobile devices have attracted the attention of many authors. The following are examples on how mobile technology helps improve collaborative work:

- Rescue efforts can be more easily coordinated in emergency situations and disaster areas [Monares et al., 2011]
- People attending a meeting can share ideas and data by means of their mobile devices [Zurita, Baloian & Baytelman, 2006].
- A team of construction workers or garden designers on a site without a network infrastructure can share blueprints and schematics [Sapateiro et al., 2011].

- Educational activities involving students and teachers can be performed in collaborative room environments [Pinkwart et al., 2003].

An important problem with developing collaborative applications for mobile devices is their heterogeneity. They vary from usual laptops, mobile phones, tablet PCs, advanced MP3 players, using different operating systems, thus providing very few possibilities for integration. As [Feisst et al., 2005] already described, these various devices implement different human-computer interaction mechanisms and use different data formats. Additionally, a major challenge in this scenario is providing applications that run on a number of different operating systems for mobile devices. As an answer to this challenge, we argue that the best strategy would be to implement platform independent applications. Currently, the most promising approach seems to build applications based on HTML5 with JavaScript.

Until now, the standard way to develop a Web-based application was by implementing multiple views, each one presenting a different functionality to the user. Each interaction with the application would, in most cases, generate a request to the server who would respond with a new page containing the changes resulting from running a piece of code. By using JavaScript and the advanced features of HTML5 like *WebDatabase*, *WebSockets*, *Canvas*, *LocalStorage*, and *LocalFileSystem*, it is now possible to develop more complex applications running inside the browser that are eventually capable of implementing rich interaction with the user in a single view and requiring less interaction with the server.

5 Implementing the Coupled Objects Paradigm With HTML5

Given the current trends on the development of mobile applications, it becomes necessary to count on an implementation of *MatchMaker*, which supports the synchronization of applications running on mobile devices with different operating systems. It also requires supporting the synchronization of applications running on mobile devices with applications running on desktop-based and tablet computers, or even any computer device. Given these requirements we opted for developing a new version for coupling applications developed in HTML5, thus being able to support the conversion of single-user application to multi-user applications for devices running an HTML5 compatible browser, without having to rewrite a particular implementation of the middleware.

The HTML5-based *MatchMaker* implementation shares an important feature with the previous one using Web Services: the client-server communication is implemented using the HTTP protocol. This means the client is responsible for taking the initiative for any communication that is needed. In fact, the implementation strongly relies on the JavaScript function `setInterval(func, time)`, which schedules a call to a function called `func` every `time` milliseconds. Although JavaScript does not have a suitable object model that can be used in this scenario, there is a library called JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) defining a very useful one.

5.1 Object Coupling with HTML5

When developing the foundations of the architecture, the following requirements need to be accomplished:

- *Coupling DOM Nodes*: when a browser processes an HTML page, a node in the Document Object Model (DOM) represents each component. These nodes can be accessed and modified through JavaScript, thus having total control over the page structure. Therefore, coupling the DOM nodes should be considered when coupling HTML-based application interfaces.
- *Event-based Synchronization*: since all the previous implementations of *MatchMaker* use event-based synchronization, we would like to keep this approach in the new version.
- *Sessions*: in order to keep track of connections, the architecture should propose a session management mechanism where users could connect to them.
- *WebSockets*: one of the limitations in the SOAP implementation of object coupling is that it turns out necessary to emulate how messages are received from the server through periodical queries. However, HTML5 defines the *WebSockets* structure, which are bidirectional communication channels allowing the server to send messages to clients without the need to ask for them.
- *Protocol Switching*: switching the main communication protocol from RMI to SOAP in the last implementation of *MatchMaker* required a considerable effort. Therefore, a new implementation should allow communication protocol switching with the least effort possible.

However, when envisioning an implementation based on the previous list of requirements, two issues arise:

- *Creating new objects to couple*: if we only couple objects through their states, it would eventually turn out difficult to manage the creation of new coupled objects. This happens because the creation of a new object should be implemented as a state change in an object that is already coupled in order to propagate this message to the other clients. That way, we need to use at least an object that has a reference to all the others, and manage as well the creation or deletion of objects as a change on their states.
- *WebSockets is not fully integrated into all the Web browsers*: even though the use of WebSockets will turn out as the best solution to implement the communication protocol, it is not well supported by the majority of Web browsers today.

Therefore, for this HTML5 implementation of *MatchMaker*, we will lengthen the original list of requirements in order to consider the following features needed to correctly support object coupling:

- *Selective Coupling*: developers should be able to choose between coupling DOM Nodes or JavaScript objects. When using DOM Nodes, the developer should use event callbacks to couple the nodes. When using JavaScript objects, the developer should use methods to send the coupling messages.
- *Mixed Synchronization*: the architecture should support both event and state-driven synchronization. That way, there would be no further problems when creating new objects, since this can be modeled as an event rather than a state change.
- *Multiple Protocols*: since HTML5 will eventually become a Web standard, the use of *WebSockets* should be seen as a strong recommendation. Therefore, communication should be implemented through *WebSockets* and a backup protocol, in case the Web browser does not properly support the former.

5.2 Communication Management

In order to develop applications using the proposed architecture and couple already-implemented applications, it is important to keep a broad separation between the business logic of the intended application and the synchronization mechanisms offered by the architecture. In order to achieve this, we need to use two *handlers*: the first one deals with JavaScript objects modifying their methods, thus integrating the communication process; the second one enables the communication process as an event-manager (such as the `onClick` event triggered by an HTML button). Therefore, in order to trigger the synchronization between coupled objects, the intended application should follow these simple steps:

- Initializing communication with server;
- Joining a session; and
- Coupling the desired objects.

In order to manage communication processes, we used a client-server architecture. In this architecture, the server publishes two interfaces to be used by the client: one for managing sessions, and another for synchronizing objects.

5.3 Server-Side Implementation

With the implementation of the server application we aim to cover three particular issues in the design of this architecture: (1) to provide a structural basis to develop distributed collaborative systems in an easy way by integrating different communication protocols; (2) to provide support for event-based synchronization; and (3) to provide new alternatives to particular cases of synchronization, where both the client and the server can be accommodated, thus being easily able to transform mono-user applications into multi-user ones.

The proposed architecture manages the different messages ensuring they are validated, persisted and propagated to their correct clients. In order to avoid leaving clients waiting for an answer, this mechanism is implemented in an asynchronous way. Therefore, when processing a message, it is queued and waiting to be sent. It is

persisted afterwards. The server also monitors concurrency, being in charge of receiving the different calls and deciding when to propagate them.

When the server receives a message, before queuing it, the server can validate the message through a state manager, which can eventually have other validators that will be in charge of deciding if the message is effectively valid or not. If the message is not valid, it is discarded and this answer is propagated through the client who initially sent the message.

If two different clients who aim to modify the same element simultaneously send two messages to the server, an inconsistency issue could arise. What one client sees is actually different from what another client is seeing. In order to solve this issue, the server evaluates if there is any risk of causing conflict with messages that are not actually being sent. If there is conflict, the server notifies the client, the message is not discarded and it is finally queued as an echoed message. An echoed message is also sent to the client. Therefore, if it is an event, it will be executed only if it is received as an echo, thus respecting the execution order. If it is a change, it cannot be discarded, but this is not an issue since the original state change will not modify the process. Figure 1 shows the server architecture.

The following list summarizes the steps to implement the server application:

- *Define one or more communication protocols, and the entry points and adapters:* when defining a protocol, it is also necessary to consider adapters and entry points linked to it, which will be in charge of receiving and interpreting the client messages in order to be processed by the server. An adapter is the component that the server uses to receive and send messages from/to clients. The interface provided by an adapter is published through the clients by an entry point. An entry point is a communication interface, in a particular protocol, which publishes the required functions to be used by a client in order to use a particular interface (in this case, the adapter). A client recognizes different entry points according to their URLs. That way, two entry points for two different protocols can coexist in a same server, thus being accessed through different URLs.
- *Define persistence and validation strategies:* since we expect the server to support state and event-based coupling, we need to manage the persistence of a single state for each object in the server. Therefore, the architecture provides a state manager specific for each case. This manager can process each received message and use it for updating the state of pertinent objects, thus generating the necessary messages for updating the state of a particular object when any adapter couples it.
- *Define a session management strategy, its protocol and entry point:* in order to group different clients, we extend the session functionality, introduced by the RMI and SOAP implementations of *MatchMaker*. Therefore, a client can either create a new session, or join an existing one. Therefore, the messages will only be propagated through clients that belong to a same session.

Figure 1: Server-side architecture

The coupled object server is in charge of managing the message flow among clients. By clients we mean the applications that should be coupled using this paradigm. In order to provide a solution for a wide range of scenarios we followed an extensible approach in order to support the usage of various different client-server communication protocols. For this, the server is composed of two components: a core component called **coupledObjectServer**, that implements common functionalities for all scenarios, and another that should be extended or modified if the developer wants to change or include a new protocol for client-server communication. The implementation presented in this work uses mainly the http protocol to support the use of HTML5 at the clients' computers.

The main element of this component is the **CouplingManager** class, which is in charge of receiving and propagating the messages. The interaction with this class is implemented through the **Adapter** interface. The creation of new **CouplingManager** instances and the access to them is implemented through the **SessionManager** interface.

The class implementing the **Adapter** interface receives the messages from the clients and will pass them to the corresponding **CouplingManager** and vice versa. The HTML5 implementation of this class uses JSON messages from the client. Therefore the class implementing this adapter is called **JSONMessageAdapter** and their functionalities are published (made accessible to http clients) by a J2EE servlet. This adapter has the particular characteristic that instead of sending information directly to the client, it stores the messages in a buffer waiting for the client's request, thus adjusting the process to the request/response model of HTTP. Figure 2 shows the UML sequence diagram for messages since they are originated at the coupled object until they reach the coupling manager.

The class implementing the **SessionManager** interface offers functionalities for creating new clients, new sessions (each one with an own **CouplingManager**) and for data management. The HTML5 implementation of this class is called **GenericSessionManager** because it implements these functions in a generic way. The functionalities for joining and leaving a session are published by a J2EE servlet.

Creation of clients and sessions is automatically managed. Figure 3 shows the UML sequence diagram of the creation and joining of a session procedure.

Figure 2: Sequence diagram of the message flow since they originate at the client, triggered by a change in a coupled object, until it reaches the coupling manager at the server

Figure 3: Sequence diagram of the session life-cycle. Its creation is requested from the client until the client joins it.

5.4 Client-Side Implementation

As we see, an application developed with the coupled object paradigm uses a standard, centralized message propagation strategy, which consists in each client generating messages that are sent to the central server, which delivers it to the final destination. However, the coupled objects paradigm and particularly its HTML5 implementation offers a mechanism which allows a developer to define what, how and when a message should be sent to other applications. This is done by transforming normal objects into coupled objects during the application's runtime.

In the coupled objects paradigm messages are sent and/or received and processed by coupled objects. These objects are normal application objects that are modified to give them additional functionalities for sending and receiving messages. In previous implementations, objects had to be defined as such in the program itself in order to allow them to be coupled during runtime. In the HTML5 implementation it is possible to transform any common object during runtime. This transformation is done inside the *ClientAdapter* class, which receives an instance of an object and then modifies its inner code, without altering its interface, in order to grant it the coupling feature. At the same time it builds a *Handler* inside the object, which will be in charge of implementing the communication between the object and the server. Figure 4 shows this process.

Figure 4: Schema for converting a normal object into a coupled one.

This strategy allows a very easy conversion of applications which have been developed for a single-user scenario into a multi-user one without modifying its code, thus allowing it to swiftly and flawlessly switch from one scenario to the other. This implementation is also very easy to use from the point of view of the application developer, but nevertheless it is also very versatile because it allows a developer to choose which cases and types of messages will be generated in order to implement the coupling feature. Firstly, the developer can choose if the coupling messages will transmit a message describing the event the object received or the state the object has.

State messages contain a complete representation of the object characterized by its instance variables. An object receiving a message like this will modify all its instance values by those of the message corresponding to the instance variables of the sender object. To use these types of messages it is necessary to define two functions: *getState* and *setState*, which can be defined by the code of the object itself (like in the previous implementations of coupled objects) or it can be defined and introduced to the object's code at the moment when the object is coupled during runtime. This is the coupling type which is recommended if the size of the object is "reasonable small".

By the size of an object we mean the size of its internal representation corresponding to the instance variables, therefore the size of an object will be the number of bytes necessary to store all the variables. It is difficult to give a concrete number for “reasonably small” since it depends on several aspects of the application itself and the environment in which it is running. Of course, using fast computers and a fast network connecting them allows handling bigger objects, but it also depends on how frequently the application needs to send and/or receive messages from the others. State messages should be chosen in order to avoid some coordination problems because it has fewer problems at the moment of handling latecomers, since applications joining the collaborative session later will receive the current state of the object. In the case of a collaborative text editor if the latecomer receives the whole state it will receive the last version of the complete text instead of the following changes only.

Event messages represent an event that occurred on an object that modified its instance variables. Different from the state messages, these only include information about the event, which will usually be fewer than the whole state of the object. In most cases, an object will generate more messages if these are event messages instead of state messages, so its usage is recommended for objects, that given their size and nature, the definition of state might be not clear. This is especially true in objects that have a variable number of sub-objects inside like lists.

The main component in the client-side application is the Client Adapter. This object uses the same interface of the server adapters, and there is only one per client. It relies on: (1) AJAX calls to coupling or decoupling actions, defined at the URL context; and (2) the *EventSource* API provided by the HTML5 specification, that serves to emulate events that are sent by the server through periodic AJAX calls. Figure 5 shows the client architecture.

Figure 5: *Client-side architecture*

It is possible that the server validates a message sent by a client. However, if the server decides that the message is not valid, it will notify the client. Therefore, in order to follow the server validation, the client sends the message, and then it locally executes the event only if the server allows it. This is not possible with state messages since any event needs to be executed before generating a new state: here, neither the client nor the server supports the validation of state messages.

The second stage at implementing the client application is allowing message generation and managing received messages in order to complete the event and state change propagation. In order to achieve this, we used handlers coupled either to a JavaScript object or a DOM element. Handlers are used to: (1) couple to the object they are managing for sending the event or state change messages; and (2) register in

the client adapter and execute the required actions when their object receives a message. A same object can have one or more different handlers for more precise control over how the coupling is performed. In this architecture we support two kinds of handlers:

- *Object Handlers*: designed to couple JavaScript objects by accessing their methods. When it is linked to an object, it can intervene over its functions to send the corresponding message by creating and assigning functions at runtime through JavaScript.
- *Bind Handlers*: designed to manage coupling with callback or binding functions when a particular event is triggered. By using JQuery, a JavaScript library, we can perform this kind of binding either with DOM nodes or with JQuery objects that can define their own events. As opposed to object handlers, a bind handler can only execute callback functions linked to a particular event, and cannot reproduce the event itself.

In order to simplify the use of the client API, we provide a JQuery plugin called *coupler*. This plugin offers a unified interface for coupling objects, encapsulating the creation and registration of handlers. To summarize, Figure 6 shows the global architecture of the communication process.

Figure 6: The Global architecture

6 Using the Proposed Architecture

In this section, we show how to design and develop distributed collaborative applications using a particular implementation of the HTML5-based *MatchMaker* architecture. First we explain how the various components of the architecture were

implemented to have a simple way to couple objects existing on a browser running an HTML5 page with JavaScript.

The components of the architecture were implemented in the following way:

- *Protocol*: since the majority of current browsers do not fully support the *WebSockets* structure as a communication channel, we implemented a HTTP-based protocol based on POST and GET queries to send and fetch information to/from the server.
- *Adapter*: we implemented an adapter that will receive the messages in JSON and will internally transform them into messages that are understandable by the objects.
- *Entry point*: we used a Servlet mapping to three different URIs: `coupling`, for sending and asking for messages to the server; `couple`, to couple an object; and `decouple`, for decoupling an object. We managed errors with HTTP status messages using the HTML5 current specification.
- *Persistence*: each object is automatically persisted, instead of using a method for achieving this.
- *Sessions and clients*: sessions are shared between many clients, instead of being attached to only one. That way, each time an HTTP session is created, we link a user to it and we manage its lifecycle with the object coupling.
- *Entry point*: since a user can only connect to a client in a new session, or over an existing session, the management of creation and assignation of these is blind for users. In order to achieve this, we implemented a Servlet that used a particular URI: if it gets a GET query, it checks the identifier of the particular model to be accessed. We then register the user, obtained through the HTTP session and respond to the client with the HTML code that implements the client for the application, where we include the relevant user data.

With this implementation, object coupling is achieved in the following way:

- Initializing communication with server:

```
var adapter=new ClientAdapter(ServerURL);
```

The `ServerURL` parameter is a string with the URL where the coupling server is located (for example, `http://saduewa.dcc.uchile.cl/HTML5Server`).
- Join a session:

```
adapter.joinSession(ssid);
```

The parameter `ssid` is a string with a name for a session. All objects registered in the same session will be coupled among them.
- Couple the desired object:
For JavaScript (JSON) objects we use:

```
adapter.coupleJSONObject(object, type);
```

The parameter `object` is a reference to the object to be coupled. The `type` parameter specifies if the coupling is by event or by state.

In the case of DOM Objects with callbacks (like pushdown buttons) we use:

```
adapter.coupleDOMObject(object, type);
```

Its parameters are the same as for the previous function.

- Decoupling objects:

```
adapter.decouple(object);
```

Next we present different examples of how the Coupled Objects paradigm and the HTML5-based implementation of *MatchMaker* can be used for developing collaborative applications.

6.1 Converting a complex single-user application in multi-user: *Mobiz*

Business Process Modeling (BPM) allows organizations to support the abstraction of business processes from technology infrastructures. It initially focused on the automation of business process, the coordination of tasks and the management of data and other resources, such as human-driven processes in which human interaction takes place in series or parallel with the use of technology [Sheth et al., 1996]. Authors have identified the lack of flexibility as one recurrent problem for process elicitation. In order to support an agile process elicitation procedure we developed a mobile collaborative application named *Mobiz*. [Baloian et al., 2013] This application will help leverage business process models on the way using mobile devices, thus allowing the construction and edition of process models in a collaborative way. Figure 7 shows the main user interface of *Mobiz*.

Figure 7: *Mobiz* user interface

The look and feel of the desktop interface was partially based on the one proposed by the BIZAGI process developer [<http://www.bizagi.com/>], mainly because it is a well-known product in the business processing environment. Thus, process engineers will rapidly learn to use the new tool. Furthermore, the interaction principle for creating new elements of the model starting from a contextual popup menu of existing elements works very well in both the desktop and the mobile environments. One of the most interesting features of MOBIZ partially inherited from BIZAGI is the use of a context menu when interacting with an artifact on the workspace. We added some additional features in order to take further advantage of this interaction element. This contextual menu does not display actions to perform but a list of possible types of artifacts that may follow the current one on the process being constructed. This application follows the MVC (Model-Controller-View) architecture: it has a model object containing all the BPMN graph elements, which are created by the user using a controller object. A view object is in charge of displaying these elements in a canvas.

In order to turn this application into a collaborative one using the implemented architecture, we just had to couple the model object of the application. In this way, all changes made to the graph by one user of one application will be distributed to all applications that joined the session. The view module of each application is in charge of displaying all changes occurring on the model. Figure 8 shows the class diagram of the most important parts of the Mobiz application.

Figure 8: *The class diagram for the Mobiz application*

The BPMNDiagram class manages the creation (and destruction) of each element shown in the figure and maintains the relation with each created instance. Also, each instance of a class has an associated DOM node. This node receives the events generated when a change in the object has to be performed when a coupled object changed. In particular, an “<element>Created” event will be triggered and passed to a node which represents the BPMN diagram on the interface each time a new element of the diagram is created, where <element> is the type of element which has been created. Also, when an element is modified a “change” event is triggered and passed to the node representing it.

The single-user HTML5 Mobiz application is a considerably complex application with more than 1,500 program lines. However, despite its complexity it was very easy to convert it to a multi-user application using the coupled object implementation described in this work by just adding the following piece of code:

```
//Initialize adapter
var adapter=new ClientAdapter(serverUrl);
//Join session
adapter.joinSession(sessionName);
//Couple BPMNDiagramInstance
adapter.coupleObject('diagram',bpmnDiagram.element,{messageType:'EVENT'});
//Listen to element creation events
jQuery(bpmnDiagram.element).bind(
    'taskCreated relationshipCreated eventCreated gatewayCreated',
    function(event,object){
        //All created elements of the diagram are //coupled at
        //creation time
        adapter.coupleBinding(object.id,object.element,{
            messageType:'STATE',
            bindings:['change']
        });
    });
});
```

6.2 Using multiple protocols and asymmetric coupling (Microblogging)

Students of a business degree program have to attend a course in which they are asked to identify situations in real contexts, for which the introduction of solutions based on Information Technology might be an opportunity to improve the life or solve a problem for citizens that frequently live, work, or travel in or around that area. They have to geographically identify spots with troubles and/or opportunities and collaboratively propose, discuss and select the most appropriate solutions.

Figure 9 shows the main view of the proposed prototype as seen on a screen of a Smartphone and a desktop computer. This application supports students performing following activities:

(1) **Information gathering and brainstorming the ideas in a divergent mode.** Students can geo-reference concrete physical locations where the proposed idea is going to be put into reality. This will include a title, a textual description and maybe pictures in order to better contextualize the proposal which has been already made public. In the Smartphone view of Figure 4 the proposal of the idea is being created.

(2) **Find alternatives, information processing and comments of alternatives using divergence and convergence modes.** In the upper part of the desktop interface view shown in Figure 9 we can see the searching tool which searches for ideas by author's name, associated comments words or date of creation. The result of the search will be shown as a list under the search tool and the corresponding location of all proposals matching the search criteria will be shown on the map.

(3) **Make choices in a convergent mode.** Each comment to a proposed idea has an associated ranking mechanism allowing students to assign points in favor or against the proposal. This mechanism can be seen in the desktop view of the interface in Figure 9, where the last comment shown at the bottom right gives two points in favor of this idea.

Figure 9: Two screenshots of the application: the small one taken from a Smartphone, and the big one from a desktop computer screen.

An interesting characteristic of this application is that it takes data from and exports data to very well known social networks like Tweeter and Facebook, since it involves users posting comments and others responding to the posts. In this way, users can interact with this application while they are connected to their preferred social network and post new comments or read those from others. On the client side, this application has the same structure as the one previously described, thus the way of coupling and decoupling objects is the same. However, for this application we used the extensibility feature of the server that was used to create an independent application (in Java) with the only purpose of posting and receiving information to and from the social networks.

In order to implement this, a second communication protocol called Hessian was developed which basically emulates a remote procedure call protocol (Like Java's RMI) but over the HTTP protocol. Figure 10 shows the structure of the classes implementing the CoupledObjectWebServer. The blue boxes show the classes provided by the generic server. The orange classes show those that were added in order to implement the interface with the social networks. We can see that since Hessian implements a HTTP protocol, it can only be initiated (executed) by a client's request. This means that the JSONMessageAdapter, which was used for the generic solution, can also be used in combination with this protocol, and that is the reason

why there was no need to implement a special new SessionManager. Figure 11 shows the architecture of the whole application.

Figure 10: The figure shows the original structure of the CoupledObjectWebServer class and the additions to implement the new protocol.

Figure 11: The figure shows the architecture of the whole application including the interface to Twitter and Facebook

6.3 CollabCode: A Collaborative Learning Scenario

This application allows a teacher to monitor student work online while the students are engaged in developing a piece of JavaScript code. It also allows him/her to leave feedback in the students' log in a web application which they can use to write a piece of code in JavaScript, run it, and see its output on the same page (see Figure 12). The student writes JavaScript code in the text area on the right side of the figure. By pressing the button labeled "Run code", the code is executed and the output is shown in the text area on the right side of the figure. By pressing the button labeled "Get code", the student gets the modifications made by the teacher.

Figure 12: CollabCode students interface

On the other hand, the teacher's interface shows a set of buttons, one for every student that has logged in and labeled with the student's ID. The teacher can display or hide code that is being developed by the student by pressing the respective button. The teacher can also write/correct the code with the student by pressing the "Save" button (see Figure 13). On the left side of the teacher's interface there are buttons for displaying/hiding the code for each student. At the right side it shows the students' code labeled with their respective ID.

Figure 13: CollabCode teacher's interface

In order to develop the students' application with *MatchMaker*, it is necessary first to provide a login page where each participating student provides his ID. This ID will be later used to identify each student's application. Then, an HTML5 page is loaded which renders the interface shown in Figure 12. This page has a JavaScript piece of code that declares a variable named after the student's ID. It then adds a String attribute to be synchronized with the student's text area where the code is being written. This variable will be registered with the server as a coupled object. Each time the "Run code" button is pressed the current code is submitted to the server. By pressing the "Get code" button the code currently stored will be retrieved and displayed. This can be used to "download" the code with modifications added by the teacher.

In order to make these two applications collaborative, each time a new student starts an application the teacher's application gets a message in order to create the necessary objects to show the new student's workspace. Then the student's and the teacher's applications join a new session in order to couple their respective buttons and text areas.

6.4 Collaborative Sketching Scenario

There are many mobile computing scenarios where collaborative sketching might help accomplish the common goal (see [Zurita, Baloian & Baytelman, 2006] for example). With this application, users can utilize the touch sensitive screen of their mobile devices to collaboratively draw sketches with a stylus or the finger. Such an application may generate a lot of traffic from the clients to the server and back. Therefore, this application was also developed to test the robustness of the HTML5-based *MatchMaker* under such conditions.

The application consists of a single webpage that is downloaded by all participants. The JavaScript code captures all *mousedown*, *mousemove* and *mouseup* events, registering their coordinates and drawing lines among these points in order to render the sketch. To make this application collaborative, a JSON object containing an array is created where all points corresponding to a single stroke are recorded. This object is coupled with the server. Every time a sketch is completed (*mouseup* event) the object state is updated at the server. At the same time, and every 200ms, the application retrieves the new version of the object and draws the new stroke on the *Canvas* element, adding this one to all previously drawn.

Since the key of the JSON array object is the same for all application instances, each user will retrieve the new stroke, no matter from whom it originated. In order to distinguish the user who generated the stroke, the JSON object also contains the user ID. In this way, the color of the stroke will be chosen according to this information. For collaborative applications where the interaction between users is synchronous and a lot of traffic is generated, the response time is critical for their usability.

To analyze the delay for updating the sketch status we conducted an experiment measuring the round trip time between client and server for 120 JSON objects containing strokes of various sizes, sending a stroke every 2 milliseconds. The size in kb of the JSON objects representing the strokes varied from 1.0 to 1.5. The average response time was 55 milliseconds with a standard deviation of 30 milliseconds, which can be considered good for human users.

7 Conclusions and Future Work

This article reports on an architecture to support the design and development of distributed collaborative applications using HTML5. The motivation for this development was the need for a suitable middleware that could simplify the development of this kind of application in mobile scenarios. Nowadays, available mobile technologies are vast and heterogeneous, requiring that such a middleware be as portable as possible. The strategy was to implement the Coupled Objects approach, which has shown to be simple, flexible and powerful, but this time using HTML5, which allows the implementation to be highly portable. This particular feature of HTML5 allowed us to develop a multi-platform mobile application based on the proposed architecture.

We claim that HTML5 is a promising technology for developing compatible collaborative applications for mobile scenarios. However, it has not been fully adopted by all browsers yet. Google Chrome, Opera and Firefox are among those that include most of the features. Even with these browsers there are some important features still not implemented, like the *WebSockets*. This is the reason why they were not used in this implementation of *MatchMaker*. *WebSockets* allow a bidirectional communication between server and client (browser) thus liberating the client for periodically polling the server in order to retrieve the latest state of coupled objects.

References

- [Aldunate et al., 2006] Aldunate, R., Ochoa, S., Peña-Mora, F., Nussbaum, M.: "Robust mobile ad hoc space for collaboration to support disaster relief efforts involving critical physical infrastructure." *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, 20, pp.13-27, 2006
- [Andrews, 1999] Andrews, G.: *Foundations of parallel and distributed programming*: Addison-Wesley Longman Publishing Co., Inc. 1999.
- [Baloian, Pino, & Jansen 2007] Baloian, N., Pino, J. A., Jansen, M.: "Implementing the coupled objects paradigm for synchronizing distributed applications through firewalls." in *Computer Supported Cooperative Work in Design III*, Springer, pp. 599-608, 2007.
- [Baloian et al., 2013] Baloian, N., Pino, J. A., Reveco, C., Zurita, G.: "Mobile Collaboration for Business Process Elicitation from an Agile Development Methodology Viewpoint", in *Proceedings of the ICEBE 2013*, pp. 306-311, 2013.
- [Dewan, 1995] Dewan, P. "Multiuser architectures." Pp. 247-270 in *Proceedings of the IFIP TC2/WG2. 7 Working Conference on Engineering for Human-Computer Interaction*: Chapman & Hall, Ltd., 1995.
- [Dewan & Choudhary, 1992] Dewan, P. & Choudhary, R.: "A high-level and flexible framework for implementing multiuser user interfaces." *ACM Transactions on Information Systems (TOIS)*, 10, pp. 345-380, 1992.
- [Ellis, Gibbs, & Rein, 1991] Ellis, C., Gibbs, S., Rein, G.: "Groupware: some issues and experiences." *Communications of the ACM*, 34, pp. 39-58, 1991.
- [Feisst et al., 2005] Feisst, M., Rodrigues dos Santos, D., Mitic, J., Christ, A.: "Adaptive Heterogeneous Learning System." *Proc. of the 4th World Conference on Mobile Learning (mLearn)*, Cape Town, South Africa, 2005, retrieved from

<http://www.mlearn.org/mlearn2005/CD/papers/Feist.pdf>, January 2015.

[Ghosh, 2006] Ghosh, S.: "Distributed systems: an algorithmic approach." *Chapman & Hall/CRC computer and information science series*.

[Grüneberger, 2012] Grüneberger, F. J.: "Real-time Collaboration Support for JavaScript Frameworks," Minor Thesis, Technical University of Dreden, Faculty of Computer Science, Germany, 2012.

[Guerrero & Fuller, 2001] Guerrero, L., Fuller, D.: "A pattern system for the development of collaborative applications." *Information and Software Technology*, 43, pp. 457-467, 2001.

[Hickson, 2011] Hickson, I "HTML5-A vocabulary and associated APIs for HTML and XHTML, W3C Working Draft 25 May 2011." *World Wide Web Consortium*. <http://www.w3.org/TR/html5/> (last visited 1 January 2014).

[Hill, et al., 1994] Hill, R., Brinck, T., Rohall, S., Patterson, J., Wilner, W.: "The Rendezvous architecture and language for constructing multiuser applications." *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction (TOCHI)*, 1, pp. 81-125, 1994.

[Hoppe et al., 2000] Hoppe, H. U., Lingnau, A., Machado, I., Paiva, A., Prada, R., Tewissen, F.: "Supporting collaborative activities in computer integrated classrooms-the NIMIS approach." in *Groupware, 2000. CRIWG 2000. Proceedings. Sixth International Workshop on: IEEE*, pp. 94-101, 2000.

[Lukosch, 2002] Lukosch, S.: "Adaptive and transparent data distribution support for synchronous groupware." in *Groupware: Design, Implementation, and Use*: Springer, pp. 255-274, 2002.

[Lukosch, 2003] Lukosch, 2003. "Transparent latecomer support for synchronous groupware." in *Groupware: Design, Implementation, and Use*, Springer, pp. 26-41, 2003.

[Monares et al., 2011] Monares, A., Ochoa, S., Pino, J. A., Herskovic, V., Rodriguez-Covili, J., Neyem, A.: "Mobile computing in urban emergency situations: Improving the support to firefighters in the field." *Expert systems with applications*, 38, 1255-1267, 2011.

[Osmani, 2013] Osmani, A.: *Developing Backbone.js Applications*, O'Reilly, 2013.

[Patterson, 1995] Patterson, J."A taxonomy of architectures for synchronous groupware applications." *ACM SIGOIS Bulletin*, 15, pp. 27-29, 1995.

[Pinkwart et al., 2003] Pinkwart, N., Hoppe, H. U., Milrad, M., Perez, J.: "Educational scenarios for cooperative use of Personal Digital Assistants." *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 19, pp.383-391, 2003.

[Roseman & Greenberg, 1996] Roseman, M., Greenberg, S.: "Building real-time groupware with GroupKit, a groupware toolkit." *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction (TOCHI)*, 3, 66-106, 1996.

[Roth & Unger, 2000] Roth, J., Unger, K.: "An extensible classification model for distribution architectures of synchronous groupware."in *Designing Cooperative Systems: the Use of Theories and Models, Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on the Design of Cooperative Systems (COOP'00)*, pp. 113-127, 2000.

[Sapateiro, et al., 2011] Sapateiro, C., Baloian, N., Antunes, P., Zurita, G.: "Developing a Mobile Collaborative Tool for Business Continuity Management.", *Journal of Universal Computer Systems (J. UCS)*, 17, pp. 164-182, 2011.

[Sheth et al., 1996] Sheth, A., Georgakopoulos, D., Joosten, S., Rusinkiewicz, M., Scacchi, W.,

- Wileden, J., Wolf, A.: "Report from the NSF workshop on workflow and process automation in information systems." *ACM SIGMOD Record*, 25, pp. 55-67, 1996.
- [Sirinivasan, 1995] Srinivasan, R.: RPC: Remote Procedure Call Protocol Specification Version 2. Internet RFC 1831, 1995.
- [Strom et al., 1998] Strom, R., Banavar G., Miller, K., Prakash, A., Ward, M.: "Concurrency control and view notification algorithms for collaborative replicated objects." *Computers, IEEE Transactions on*, 47, pp. 458-471, 1998.
- [Tewissen et al., 2000] Tewissen, F., Baloian, N., Hoppe, H. U., Reimberg, E.: "MatchMaker: synchronising objects in replicated software-architectures." in *Groupware, 2000. CRIWG 2000. Proceedings. Sixth International Workshop on*: IEEE, pp. 60-67, 2000.
- [Urnes & Nejabi, 1994] Urnes, T. & Nejabi, R.: "Tools for implementing groupware: Survey and evaluation." Technical report CS-94-03, Department of Computer Science, York University, Toronto, Canada, 1994.
- [Vogel & Duddy, 1995] Vogel, A. & Duddy, K.: *Java Programming with CORBA*. 2nd. ed. Wiley & Sons, 1998.
- [Zhao & Hoppe, 1994] Zhao, J., Hoppe, H. U.: "Supporting flexible communication in heterogeneous multi-user environments." in *Distributed Computing Systems, 1994., Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on*: IEEE, pp. 442-449, 1994.
- [Zurita, Baloian & Baytelman, 2006] Zurita, G., Baloian, N., Baytelman, F.: "A face-to-face system for supporting mobile collaborative design using sketches and pen-based gestures." in *Computer Supported Cooperative Work in Design, 2006. CSCWD'06. 10th International Conference on*: IEEE, pp. 1-6, 2006.